

Supplemental Information for:

Community Composition of Bacteria Isolated from Swiss Banknotes Varies Depending on Collection Environment

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Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Number of reads per sample. The figure shows the number of reads for each sample retained after filtering. Total reads per sample varied greatly, with 140 reads for the butcher in BRI and 7'152'829 reads for the florist in BRI (~51'092x difference). Note: y-axis is log₁₀-transformed. Abbreviations: BIA = Biasca, BRI = Brienz BE, FRI = Frick, KLO = Klosters-Serneus, LAN = Langnau am Albis, ORB = Orbe, POR = Porrentruy, ROR = Rorschach, STE = Stein am Rhein, VIS = Visp.

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Supplementary Figure 2. Venn diagram of unique and shared core ZOTUs in samples from banknotes collected in various shop types across Switzerland. Each ellipse gives the number of ZOTUs present at an abundance of >0.1% in >50% of a set of banknotes attributed to a certain shop type. Numbers in overlapping areas of ellipses indicate core ZOTUs shared between sets of banknotes collected in different types of shops. The seven core microbiome ZOTUs present in >50% of every set of banknotes were attributed to the genera: *Corynebacterium*, *Escherichia-Shigella*, *Propionibacterium*, *Pseudomonas*, *Streptococcus* (n = 2), and *Staphylococcus*.

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Supplementary Figure 3. Bacterial community composition across sampling locations and shop types at Genus level. Relative abundances of the main bacterial genera identified by amplicon sequencing from banknotes sampled in each shop (lower x-axis) and location (upper x-axis, indicated by three-letter abbreviations). *Unknown* contains non-assigned ZOTUs; *Other* contains assigned ZOTUs not belonging to the most abundant genera. The colour for genera corresponds to the colour for family in Fig. 1, except for *Kocuria* and *Rothia* which also belong to the family *Micrococcaceae*. Abbreviations: BIA = Biasca, BRI = Brienz BE, FRI = Frick, KLO = Klosters-Serneus, LAN = Langnau am Albis, ORB = Orbe, POR = Porrentruy, ROR = Rorschach, STE = Stein am Rhein, VIS = Visp.

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Supplementary
Figure 4.

Supplementary Figure 4. Heatmap of the 163 ZOTUs occurring across samples. Darker colours indicate higher abundance of the respective ZOTU in the sample (number of reads, rlog-transformed data). The order of samples on the x-axis is ordination-based, i.e. more similar samples cluster together. The red rectangle comprises the six butcher samples clustering together in Fig. 3. Abbreviations: BIA = Biasca, BRI = Brienz BE, FRI = Frick, KLO = Klosters-Serneus, LAN = Langnau am Albis, ORB = Orbe, POR = Porrentruy, ROR = Rorschach, STE = Stein am Rhein, VIS = Visp.

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Supplementary Figure 5. Cluster dendrogram (hierarchical clustering) of the 42 samples. The red rectangle comprises the the six butcher samples clustering together in Fig. 3. Abbreviations: BIA = Biasca, BRI = Brienz BE, FRI = Frick, KLO = Klosters-Serneus, LAN = Langnau am Albis, ORB = Orbe, POR = Porrentruy, ROR = Rorschach, STE = Stein am Rhein, VIS = Visp.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1. Supplementary information on locations. The table lists supplementary information on the ten towns in Switzerland in which banknotes were collected. The linked map contains the symbols for all shops in a town from which banknotes were collected.

Location	Location abbreviation	Canton	Postcode	Inhabitants (2018)*	Inhabitants/sqkm (2018) *	Map Notes
Orbe	ORB	Waadt	1350	6938	575.8	https://s.geo.admin.ch/8f4c69a36b
Porrentruy	POR	Jura	2900	6678	452.4	https://s.geo.admin.ch/8f9521d981
Brienz	BRI	Bern	3855	3092	64.3	https://s.geo.admin.ch/8f4c70430c
Visp	VIS	Wallis	3930	7950	602.3	https://s.geo.admin.ch/8f4c7222fa
Frick	FRI	Aargau	5070	5564	558.6	https://s.geo.admin.ch/8f4ccde809
Biasca	BIA	Tessin	6710	6115	103.5	https://s.geo.admin.ch/8f620d5170
Klosters	KLO	Graubünden	7250	4451	20.3	https://s.geo.admin.ch/8f4c7a3ba8
Langnau a. Albis	LAN	Zürich	8135	7547	870.5	https://s.geo.admin.ch/8f4c7be11d
Stein a. Rhein	STE	Schaffhausen	8260	3415	590.8	https://s.geo.admin.ch/8f8ac5922b
Rorschach	ROR	St Gallen	9400	9441	5303.9	https://s.geo.admin.ch/8f4c7f934b
* source: https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home/statistiken/regionalstatistik/regionale-portraits-kennzahlen/gemeinden/gemeindeportraits.html						

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Supplementary Table 2. Supplementary information on samples. The table lists supplementary information on the fifty banknote samples collected for this study. The column headings are: Denomination = banknotes value ; Series = number of Swiss banknotes series ; Issue year = year banknote was issued ; Collection date/hour = date/hour of banknote collection ; Extraction day/batch = day/batch of DNA extraction ; Location = town banknote was collected in ; Lat/Long_WGS84 = coordinates in WGS format; Shop type = shop type banknote was collected in. The location abbreviations are: BIA = Biasca, BRI = Brienz BE, FRI = Frick, KLO = Klosters-Serneus, LAN = Langnau am Albis, ORB = Orbe, POR = Porrentruy, ROR = Rorschach, STE = Stein am Rhein, VIS = Visp.

Sample ID	Denomination	Series	Issue year	Collection date	Collection hour	Extraction day	Extraction batch	Location	Lat_WGS84	Long_WGS84	Shop type
bakery-ORB	10	9	2016	03.17.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	ORB	6.53214199	46.725701	bakery
butcher-ORB	10	9	2016	03.17.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	ORB	6.5319776	46.7245842	butcher
florist-ORB	10	9	2016	03.17.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	ORB	6.53205872	46.7236492	florist
kiosk-ORB	10	9	2016	03.17.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	ORB	6.53893532	46.7215536	kiosk
pharmacy-ORB	10	9	2016	03.17.2021	10:00:00	04.01.21	3	ORB	6.53241747	46.7233192	pharmacy
bakery-POR	10	9	2016	03.25.2021	10:00:00	04.01.21	3	POR	7.07815716	47.4210245	bakery
butcher-POR	10	9	2016	03.25.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	POR	7.07322855	47.4189223	butcher
florist-POR	10	9	2016	03.25.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	POR	7.0747097	47.417425	florist
kiosk-POR	10	9	2016	03.25.2021	11:00:00	03.30.2021	2	POR	7.07743321	47.4163902	kiosk
pharmacy-POR	10	9	2016	03.25.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	POR	7.07487368	47.416697	pharmacy
bakery-BRI	10	9	2016	03.22.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	BRI	8.03353591	46.754099	bakery
butcher-BRI	10	9	2017	03.22.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	BRI	8.03155907	46.7540553	butcher
florist-BRI	10	9	2017	03.22.2021	10:00:00	04.01.21	3	BRI	8.03082675	46.754113	florist
kiosk-BRI	10	9	2017	03.22.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	BRI	8.03893735	46.7549073	kiosk
pharmacy-BRI	10	9	2016	03.22.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	BRI	8.03229357	46.7541954	pharmacy
bakery-VIS	10	9	2016	03.16.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	VIS	7.88191502	46.2931997	bakery
butcher-VIS	10	9	2016	03.16.2021	10:00:00	04.01.21	3	VIS	7.88126083	46.2925456	butcher
florist-VIS	10	9	2016	03.16.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	VIS	7.88144706	46.2915104	florist

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kiosk-VIS	10	9	2017	03.16.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	VIS	7.88133545	46.2937417	kiosk
pharmacy-VIS	10	9	2016	03.16.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	VIS	7.8814024	46.2924011	pharmacy
bakery-FRI	10	9	2016	03.12.21	09:00:00	03.29.2021	1	FRI	8.02164707	47.5069565	bakery
butcher-FRI	10	9	2016	03.12.21	09:00:00	03.30.2021	2	FRI	8.02079112	47.5075814	butcher
florist-FRI	10	9	2016	03.12.21	09:00:00	03.29.2021	1	FRI	8.02188618	47.5069733	florist
kiosk-FRI	10	9	2016	03.12.21	09:00:00	03.30.2021	2	FRI	8.01281878	47.5068387	kiosk
pharmacy-FRI	10	9	2016	03.12.21	09:00:00	04.01.21	3	FRI	8.01891388	47.5082833	pharmacy
bakery-BIA	10	9	2016	03.15.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	BIA	8.97059518	46.359882	bakery
butcher-BIA	10	9	2016	03.15.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	BIA	8.97256158	46.3535842	butcher
florist-BIA	10	9	2016	03.15.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	BIA	8.97168021	46.3578069	florist
kiosk-BIA	10	9	2016	03.15.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	BIA	8.97440663	46.3512829	kiosk
pharmacy-BIA	10	9	2016	03.15.2021	10:00:00	04.01.21	3	BIA	8.96984933	46.360162	pharmacy
bakery-KLO	10	9	2016	03.24.2021	10:00:00	04.01.21	3	KLO	9.88355785	46.8670851	bakery
butcher-KLO	10	9	2016	03.24.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	KLO	9.88288202	46.8701145	butcher
florist-KLO	10	9	2016	03.24.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	KLO	9.88302037	46.8670966	florist
kiosk-KLO	10	9	2016	03.24.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	KLO	9.88156669	46.8686036	kiosk
pharmacy-KLO	10	9	2016	03.24.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	KLO	9.8820039	46.8678293	pharmacy
bakery-LAN	10	9	2016	03.13.2021	11:00:00	03.29.2021	1	LAN	8.54303664	47.2873209	bakery
butcher-LAN	10	9	2016	03.13.2021	11:00:00	03.30.2021	2	LAN	8.53988255	47.2888713	butcher
florist-LAN	10	9	2016	03.13.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	LAN	8.53822798	47.2881315	florist
kiosk-LAN	10	9	2016	03.13.2021	11:00:00	03.29.2021	1	LAN	8.54375951	47.2871161	kiosk
pharmacy-LAN	10	9	2016	03.13.2021	10:00:00	04.01.21	3	LAN	8.53897478	47.2890869	pharmacy
bakery-STE	10	9	2016	03.23.2021	09:00:00	03.30.2021	2	STE	8.8585099	47.6594565	bakery
butcher-STE	10	9	2016	03.23.2021	09:00:00	04.01.21	3	STE	8.85894447	47.659775	butcher
florist-STE	10	9	2016	03.23.2021	09:00:00	03.29.2021	1	STE	8.85433058	47.6590038	florist

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kiosk-STE	10	9	2016	03.23.2021	09:00:00	03.30.2021	2	STE	8.85515711	47.6560524	kiosk
pharmacy-STE	10	9	2016	03.23.2021	09:00:00	03.29.2021	1	STE	8.85932587	47.6595994	pharmacy
bakery-ROR	10	9	2017	03.18.2021	10:00:00	04.01.21	3	ROR	9.49191423	47.4776962	bakery
butcher-ROR	10	9	2016	03.18.2021	09:00:00	03.29.2021	1	ROR	9.49141016	47.4766705	butcher
florist-ROR	10	9	2016	03.18.2021	10:00:00	03.29.2021	1	ROR	9.49193047	47.4784607	florist
kiosk-ROR	10	9	2016	03.18.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	ROR	9.49274292	47.4785363	kiosk
pharmacy-ROR	10	9	2016	03.18.2021	10:00:00	03.30.2021	2	ROR	9.49109824	47.4778727	pharmacy

Supplementary Table 3. Number, morphology and putative identity of colonies in plated samples. The table lists the number, morphology and identity (based on identification with chromatogenic agar) of the colonies detected in plated samples (50µL aliquot on Chromatic™ MH agar plate, 24h at 37°C).

Sample ID	Number of colonies	Colony morphology	Identification
bakery-ORB	0	n.a.	n.a.
butcher-ORB	10	green/blue, small, round, cluster	<i>Klebsiella, Enterobacter, Serratia</i>
florist-ORB	2	green/turquoise, small, round	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>
kiosk-ORB	0	n.a.	n.a.
pharmacy-ORB	0	n.a.	n.a.
bakery-POR	0	n.a.	n.a.
butcher-POR	1	green/blue, small, round	<i>Klebsiella, Enterobacter, Serratia</i>
butcher-POR	1	white-ish, small, round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
florist-POR	0	n.a.	n.a.

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kiosk-POR	0	n.a.	n.a.
pharmacy-POR	2	green/blue, small, round	<i>Klebsiella, Enterobacter, Serratia</i>
pharmacy-POR	1	green/turquoise, small, round	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>
bakery-BRI	2	green/blue, small, round	<i>Klebsiella, Enterobacter, Serratia</i>
bakery-BRI	1	white-ish, small, round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
butcher-BRI	5	white-ish, small, round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
florist-BRI	0	n.a.	n.a.
kiosk-BRI	0	n.a.	n.a.
pharmacy-BRI	0	n.a.	n.a.
bakery-VIS	1	blue centre/white border, felt-ish, big (d >5mm), yeast-like	unknown
butcher-VIS	14	green/blue, small, round	<i>Klebsiella, Enterobacter, Serratia</i>
butcher-VIS	2	white-ish, small, round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
butcher-VIS	59	dark pink/red/lila, small, round	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
florist-VIS	1	dark pink/red/lila, very small, round	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
florist-VIS	1	white, translucent, big (d 4mm), yeast-like	unknown
kiosk-VIS	0	n.a.	n.a.
pharmacy-VIS	0	n.a.	n.a.
bakery-FRI	1	white-ish or light pink/red/lila, small, round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
butcher-FRI	1	dark pink/red/lila, small, round	E.coli
butcher-FRI	1	white-ish, small, round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
florist-FRI	0	n.a.	n.a.
kiosk-FRI	2	white-ish/translucent, very small, round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
pharmacy-FRI	0	n.a.	n.a.

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bakery-BIA	1	yellow/white, small, 3D/growing upwards, looks like something you would get from your nose	unknown
butcher-BIA	3	dark pink/red/lila, small, round	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
butcher-BIA	4	white-ish, big (d 3mm), round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
butcher-BIA	2	white-ish, small, round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
florist-BIA	0	n.a.	n.a.
kiosk-BIA	1	blue, translucent, big (d 1cm), irregular shape	unknown
pharmacy-BIA	0	n.a.	n.a.
bakery-KLO	0	n.a.	n.a.
butcher-KLO	13	light pink/red/lila, small, round	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
butcher-KLO	1	green/blue, small, round	<i>Klebsiella, Enterobacter, Serratia</i>
butcher-KLO	1	green/blue, big (d >5mm), dark at centre, getting lighter going outwards, astral/yeast-like	unknown
florist-KLO	0	n.a.	n.a.
kiosk-KLO	1	green/blue, small, round	<i>Klebsiella, Enterobacter, Serratia</i>
kiosk-KLO	1	white-ish, big (d 3mm), round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
pharmacy-KLO	0	n.a.	n.a.
bakery-LAN	1	white, felt-ish, big (d 5mm), with clear bubble-like centre	unknown
butcher-LAN	0	n.a.	n.a.
florist-LAN	1	white-ish, small, round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
kiosk-LAN	1	dark pink/red/lila, small, round	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
pharmacy-LAN	0	n.a.	n.a.
bakery-STE	0	n.a.	n.a.
butcher-STE	0	n.a.	n.a.

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florist-STE	9	white-ish, small, round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
florist-STE	1	light-blue, translucent, big (d 3mm), round	unknown
florist-STE	2	green/blue, small, round	<i>Klebsiella, Enterobacter, Serratia</i>
florist-STE	1	dark pink/red/lila or brown, small, round	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
kiosk-STE	1	white-ish, small, round	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
pharmacy-STE	0	n.a.	n.a.
bakery-ROR	0	n.a.	n.a.
butcher-ROR	1	green/blue, small, round	<i>Klebsiella, Enterobacter, Serratia</i>
butcher-ROR	1	dark pink/red/lila, small, round	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
florist-ROR	1	yellow/green, small, round	<i>Pseudomonas</i>
florist-ROR	1	dark pink/red/lila, big (d 3mm), round	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
kiosk-ROR	0	n.a.	n.a.
pharmacy-ROR	0	n.a.	n.a.

Supplementary Table 4. Sequences of primers used during library preparation. These primers were used to amplify the V3-V4 regions of the 16S rRNA gene during the first course of limited cycle PCR.

forward primers	
340F_nex0	TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGGCCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG
340F_nex1	TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGNGCCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG
340F_nex2	TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGNNGCCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG
340F_nex3	TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGNNNGCCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG
reverse primers	
805R_nex0	GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGTGACTACHVGGGTATCTAATCC
805R_nex1	GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGNTGACTACHVGGGTATCTAATCC
805R_nex2	GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGNNTGACTACHVGGGTATCTAATCC
805R_nex3	GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGNNNTGACTACHVGGGTATCTAATCC

Supplementary Table 5. Reads per sample before and after filtering. The table lists the read sums for each sample before and after each filtering step. Filtering step 1 (ReadSum_01 → ReadSum_02): removal of samples with read sum <1000 (n = 8, florist-KLO, butcher-POR, florist-POR, bakery-STE, florist-STE, bakery-BIA, bakery-VIS, florist-LAN). Filtering step 2 (ReadSum_02 → ReadSum_03): removal of ZOTUs present at <0.1% of total sequencing depth (results in reduction in read sum for each sample; total sequencing depth = 14'398'160). The location abbreviations are: BIA = Biasca, BRI = Brienz BE, FRI = Frick, KLO = Klosters-Serneus, LAN = Langnau am Albis, ORB = Orbe, POR = Porrentruy, ROR = Rorschach, STE = Stein am Rhein, VIS = Visp.

Sample ID	ReadSum_01	ReadSum_02	ReadSum_03	Location	Shop type
bakery-FRI	114200	114200	53760	FRI	bakery
butcher-FRI	162322	162322	93660	FRI	butcher
florist-FRI	202155	202155	42515	FRI	florist
kiosk-FRI	175437	175437	85868	FRI	kiosk
pharmacy-FRI	307244	307244	61859	FRI	pharmacy
bakery-BRI	5328	5328	3392	BRI	bakery
butcher-BRI	2060	2060	138	BRI	butcher
florist-BRI	6752341	6752341	6167513	BRI	florist
kiosk-BRI	208071	208071	198031	BRI	kiosk
pharmacy-BRI	9225	9225	6040	BRI	pharmacy
bakery-KLO	202364	202364	98592	KLO	bakery
butcher-KLO	235452	235452	179502	KLO	butcher
florist-KLO	190	NA	NA	KLO	florist
kiosk-KLO	237475	237475	118867	KLO	kiosk
pharmacy-KLO	191824	191824	97575	KLO	pharmacy
bakery-POR	308617	308617	178351	POR	bakery
butcher-POR	4	NA	NA	POR	butcher
florist-POR	219	NA	NA	POR	florist
kiosk-POR	320526	320526	257093	POR	kiosk
pharmacy-POR	345879	345879	147741	POR	pharmacy
bakery-ROR	299698	299698	179789	ROR	bakery
butcher-ROR	95170	95170	50599	ROR	butcher
florist-ROR	181294	181294	25490	ROR	florist
kiosk-ROR	305964	305964	153294	ROR	kiosk
pharmacy-ROR	114889	114889	39322	ROR	pharmacy
bakery-STE	166	NA	NA	STE	bakery
butcher-STE	324269	324269	149241	STE	butcher
florist-STE	290	NA	NA	STE	florist
kiosk-STE	94564	94564	36712	STE	kiosk

pharmacy-STE	374098	374098	171063	STE	pharmacy
bakery-BIA	23	NA	NA	BIA	bakery
butcher-BIA	281304	281304	213667	BIA	butcher
florist-BIA	68992	68992	68351	BIA	florist
kiosk-BIA	375140	375140	231005	BIA	kiosk
pharmacy-BIA	1331	1331	758	BIA	pharmacy
bakery-ORB	102777	102777	90516	ORB	bakery
butcher-ORB	154164	154164	63229	ORB	butcher
florist-ORB	65900	65900	15267	ORB	florist
kiosk-ORB	212692	212692	79226	ORB	kiosk
pharmacy-ORB	2775	2775	838	ORB	pharmacy
bakery-VIS	722	NA	NA	VIS	bakery
butcher-VIS	302458	302458	238540	VIS	butcher
florist-VIS	343588	343588	54478	VIS	florist
kiosk-VIS	167685	167685	94603	VIS	kiosk
pharmacy-VIS	223900	223900	118012	VIS	pharmacy
bakery-LAN	88027	88027	72522	LAN	bakery
butcher-LAN	258637	258637	129820	LAN	butcher
florist-LAN	18	NA	NA	LAN	florist
kiosk-LAN	2586	2586	1093	LAN	kiosk
pharmacy-LAN	175738	175738	68254	LAN	pharmacy

Supplementary Table 6. Relative abundance of the top 12 families across samples. The table lists the relative abundance (in %) of the 12 relatively most abundant families for all samples. The location abbreviations are: BIA = Biasca, BRI = Brienz BE, FRI = Frick, KLO = Klosters-Serneus, LAN = Langnau am Albis, ORB = Orbe, POR = Porrentruy, ROR = Rorschach, STE = Stein am Rhein, VIS = Visp. Latitude and longitude are given in WGS format.

Due to the size of the file this table is available separately (*suppTable_06.csv*).

Supplementary Table 7. Relative abundance of the top 12 genera across samples. The table lists the relative abundance (in %) of the 12 relatively most abundant genera for all samples. The location abbreviations are: BIA = Biasca, BRI = Brienz BE, FRI = Frick, KLO = Klosters-Serneus, LAN = Langnau am Albis, ORB = Orbe, POR = Porrentruy, ROR = Rorschach, STE = Stein am Rhein, VIS = Visp. Latitude and longitude are given in WGS format.

Due to the size of the file this table is available separately (*suppTable_07.csv*).

Supplementary Table 8. Relative abundance of shared core ZOTUs. The table lists the relative abundance (in %) of the seven dominant core ZOTUs (Dawson *et al.*, 2017; Cruaud *et al.*, 2020) shared between all shop types. Location abbreviations are: BIA = Biasca, BRI = Brienz BE, FRI = Frick, KLO = Klosters-Serneus, LAN = Langnau am Albis, ORB = Orbe, POR = Porrentruy, ROR = Rorschach, STE = Stein am Rhein, VIS = Visp.

Due to the size of the file this table is available separately (*suppTable_08.csv*).

Supplementary Table 9. NMDS scores for each of the 163 ZOTUs. The table lists the scores for each dimension (NMDS1, NMDS2) in the ordination visualisation (Fig. 3). ZOTU annotation with `format_to_besthit()` function in `microbiomeutilities` package (version 1.00.16; (Lahti *et al.*, 2017)).

ZOTU	MDS1	MDS2	ZOTU	MDS1	MDS2
ZOTU2:Escherichia-Shigella	0.05730727	-0.0327834	ZOTU142:Bradyrhizobiaceae	0.01442155	-0.0724633
ZOTU41:Streptococcus	0.05328139	-0.0106425	ZOTU172:Corynebacteriaceae	0.01340052	-0.0172705
ZOTU56:Veillonella	0.05276656	0.00339363	ZOTU79:Nocardioiodes	0.01304672	0.01741828
ZOTU140:Rothia	0.05274238	-0.0256805	ZOTU11:Saccharibacteria	0.0125994	-0.0211877
ZOTU78:Rothia	0.05192814	-0.0129222	ZOTU111:Desemzia	0.01134844	-0.0078049
ZOTU1:Pseudomonas	0.05148414	-0.0267068	ZOTU99:Corynebacteriaceae	0.01024344	0.08483568
ZOTU87:Streptococcus	0.05132028	-0.0123853	ZOTU121:Lactococcus	0.01000869	0.13337945
ZOTU3:Staphylococcus	0.05095895	-0.0171798	ZOTU31:Thermus	0.00904807	-0.0307946
ZOTU38:Propionibacterium	0.05081344	-0.0137691	ZOTU33:Flavobacterium	0.00849264	-0.0176427
ZOTU5:Streptococcus	0.0505481	-0.0118718	ZOTU169:Clostridiisalibacter	0.00797463	0.02272327
ZOTU21:Rothia	0.05037946	-0.0130542	ZOTU55:Photobacterium	0.00721648	0.09179588
ZOTU88:Corynebacteriaceae	0.05033086	-0.0269886	ZOTU46:Lactobacillales	0.00709748	-0.0191396
ZOTU6:Corynebacterium	0.05028706	-0.0113914	ZOTU92:Lactobacillus	0.00586005	0.08017116
ZOTU64:Streptococcus	0.04959371	0.01789076	ZOTU107:Sphingomonas	0.00531963	-0.0277524
ZOTU161:Lawsonella	0.04943638	-0.0271418	ZOTU163:Moraxella_sp._feline_oral_taxon_089	0.00510093	-0.0877364
ZOTU139:Granulicatella	0.04937002	-0.0219911	ZOTU166:Chloroflexi	0.0033126	-0.0779263
ZOTU89:Brochothrix	0.04828398	0.03054945	ZOTU162:Leuconostoc	0.0024969	0.10316701
ZOTU20:Gemella	0.04818861	-0.0319006	ZOTU104:Corynebacterium	0.00047779	-0.0307464
ZOTU174:Sphingomonas	0.04789879	-0.0110251	ZOTU153:Photobacterium	-0.0006998	0.13064208
ZOTU13:Staphylococcus	0.04664732	0.01109724	ZOTU160:Streptococcus	-0.002533	0.00634604
ZOTU117:Rothia	0.04656358	-0.0133407	ZOTU47:Brevibacterium	-0.0028092	0.05083274
ZOTU4:Streptococcus	0.04601654	-0.0025	ZOTU68:Enterobacteriaceae	-0.0031899	-0.03016
ZOTU44:Novosphingobium	0.04571736	-0.013307	ZOTU168:Aerococcus	-0.0036755	0.03272319
ZOTU14:Pseudomonas	0.04559882	-0.0201748	ZOTU50:Photobacterium	-0.0116215	0.20624871
ZOTU196:Corynebacterium	0.04540179	-0.0159044	ZOTU74:Brevibacterium	-0.0151122	0.10541356
ZOTU120:Haemophilus	0.04434457	-0.002158	ZOTU30:Brevibacterium	-0.0179297	0.08180127
ZOTU39:Enhydrobacter	0.04415742	-0.0152317	ZOTU17:Pseudarthrobacter	-0.0205082	-0.007437

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ZOTU49:Staphylococcus	0.04411697	0.02237678	ZOTU98:Brevibacterium	-0.0225247	0.10207496
ZOTU201:Corynebacterium	0.04313749	0.00594622	ZOTU127:Lawsonella	-0.030283	-0.0347926
ZOTU108:Anaerococcus	0.04257978	0.0075745	ZOTU138:Planifilum	-0.0321269	-0.0760371
ZOTU16:Staphylococcus	0.0424552	-0.0101929	ZOTU134:Duganella	-0.040449	0.06389764
ZOTU143:Abiotrophia	0.04154395	-0.0109499	ZOTU23:Acidimicrobiales	-0.0422583	-0.0423177
ZOTU179:Psychrobacter	0.04089985	-0.010511	ZOTU148:Lysobacter	-0.0442132	-0.0172773
ZOTU73:Kocuria	0.0406755	0.00154943	ZOTU18:Acetobacteraceae	-0.0553217	-0.0386851
ZOTU129:Paracoccus	0.04019151	0.00169117	ZOTU15:Rhizobiales	-0.0610517	-0.0337397
ZOTU28:Micrococcus	0.04012933	-0.0010915	ZOTU22:Parcubacteria	-0.0648825	-0.034022
ZOTU137:Truepera	0.03992759	-0.0462813	ZOTU173:Cellulomonadaceae	-0.0698148	-0.0404219
ZOTU109:Gemella	0.03986634	-0.0276838	ZOTU40:Anaerococcus	-0.0733416	-0.0519969
ZOTU36:Chryseobacterium	0.03854048	-0.0029423	ZOTU76:Gaiella	-0.0734224	-0.0279952
ZOTU91:Micrococcus	0.03842443	0.0044853	ZOTU54:Corynebacteriaceae	-0.0762838	0.15066023
ZOTU29:Porphyromonas	0.0367369	-0.0216445	ZOTU52:Sphingobacterium	-0.0968468	0.08088874
ZOTU133:Rhodococcus	0.03664773	0.0133623	ZOTU167:Mycobacterium	-0.1082307	0.00501021
ZOTU197:Veillonella	0.03589104	0.0294119	ZOTU61:Photobacterium	-0.1097046	0.39919256
ZOTU178:Acinetobacter	0.03515831	0.01292604	ZOTU170:Kocuria	-0.1159726	0.12922351
ZOTU125:Lactococcus	0.03512806	-0.0099691	ZOTU152:Isosphaera	-0.1162278	-0.0735077
ZOTU34:Staphylococcus	0.03496982	0.01011052	ZOTU115:Microbacteriaceae	-0.1163409	0.05872633
ZOTU37:Staphylococcus	0.03492365	-0.0137789	ZOTU128:Hymenobacter	-0.1316927	-0.1088893
ZOTU102:Fingoldia	0.03362732	-0.0045215	ZOTU124:Actinomycetospora	-0.1319739	-0.0187272
ZOTU103:Carnobacterium	0.03352972	0.0368222	ZOTU100:Photobacterium	-0.1358745	0.34840205
ZOTU118:Neisseriaceae	0.03333235	-0.0375732	ZOTU165:Halomonas	-0.1897639	0.2433281
ZOTU187:Craurococcus	0.03328822	-0.0640929	ZOTU84:Flavobacterium	-0.2049448	-0.0463485
ZOTU146:Staphylococcus	0.03184716	-0.0263628	ZOTU176:Brachybacterium	-0.2060346	0.3107196
ZOTU32:Micrococcaceae	0.03132497	-0.0046581	ZOTU171:Methylobacterium	-0.2390657	0.01347099
ZOTU70:Leuconostoc	0.03102254	0.05085632	ZOTU94:Lachnospiraceae	-0.2484112	0.01217332
ZOTU80:Acinetobacter	0.03087387	0.00694619	ZOTU112:Hymenobacter	-0.3967924	-0.0092792
ZOTU101:Peptoniphilus	0.03010505	-0.0629798	ZOTU63:OM1_clade	-0.4748172	-0.1453787
ZOTU77:Acidovorax	0.02962544	-0.031069	ZOTU72:Subdoligranulum	-0.5410566	-0.0019624
ZOTU131:Acinetobacter	0.02935586	0.0410873	ZOTU122:Gaiellaceae	-0.576009	-0.1866043
ZOTU86:Streptococcus	0.02928791	-0.0180964	ZOTU110:Singulisphaera	-0.6027149	-0.0591442
ZOTU45:Corynebacterium	0.0291601	-0.0356454	ZOTU51:Variibacter	-0.6044048	0.00423743
ZOTU82:Corynebacterium_1	0.02898465	0.04453783	ZOTU147:Pseudomonas	-0.6050551	-0.1061542
ZOTU19:Corynebacteriaceae	0.02894523	-0.0241684	ZOTU48:Stenotrophomonas	-0.6072141	-0.0522472
ZOTU8:Corynebacterium	0.02771125	0.00296455	ZOTU208:Bacilli	-0.6102026	-0.2618254

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ZOTU26: <i>Bacillus</i>	0.02751467	-0.0350773	ZOTU43: <i>Alphaproteobacteria</i>	-0.617965	-0.0669666
ZOTU66: <i>Microbacteriaceae</i>	0.02702594	-0.0200106	ZOTU149: <i>Porphyromonas</i>	-0.6389732	-0.1987567
ZOTU69: <i>Lactobacillus</i>	0.02634711	0.07936559	ZOTU25: <i>Acidiphilium</i>	-0.6904041	-0.0956538
ZOTU114: <i>Staphylococcus</i>	0.02633792	0.0349737	ZOTU157: <i>Subgroup</i>	-0.6976051	0.08155747
ZOTU119: <i>Rothia</i>	0.02466601	0.01108826	ZOTU105: <i>Bryobacter</i>	-0.7101991	-0.1281004
ZOTU154: <i>Methylobacterium</i>	0.02415951	-0.0654888	ZOTU62: <i>Tepidisphaeraceae</i>	-0.7166585	-0.0277752
ZOTU158: <i>Brevibacterium</i>	0.0235347	0.00785889	ZOTU71: <i>Acidimicrobiaceae</i>	-0.7317721	-0.084418
ZOTU126: <i>Oxalobacteraceae</i>	0.02153712	-0.0223155	ZOTU136: <i>Ktedonobacteraceae</i>	-0.7926883	-0.0885217
ZOTU58: <i>Staphylococcus</i>	0.02100687	-0.0385819	ZOTU141: <i>Chitinophagaceae</i>	-0.7999002	-0.0702119
ZOTU96: <i>Kocuria</i>	0.01949318	0.04142059	ZOTU130: <i>Saccharibacteria</i>	-0.8013313	-0.0645734
ZOTU42: <i>Intrasporangiaceae</i>	0.01923794	0.00358067	ZOTU195: <i>Hymenobacter</i>	-0.8096099	-0.079094
ZOTU192: <i>Pseudomonas</i>	0.01880303	0.00183501	ZOTU116: <i>Hymenobacter</i>	-0.8183641	-0.0809633
ZOTU113: <i>Dolosigranulum</i>	0.01840913	-0.0126963	ZOTU159: <i>Ktedonobacteraceae</i>	-0.83517	-0.0985353
ZOTU210: <i>Actinomyces</i>	0.01828953	-0.0091106	ZOTU83: <i>Hymenobacter</i>	-0.8380494	-0.0762446
ZOTU151: <i>Massilia</i>	0.01751111	-0.0482222	ZOTU90: <i>Desemzia</i>	-0.8410246	-0.0767683
ZOTU24: <i>Kocuria</i>	0.01721711	-0.0040575	ZOTU95: <i>Saccharibacteria</i>	-0.8528812	-0.0802721
ZOTU12: <i>Turicella</i>	0.01719001	-0.0002162			
ZOTU97: <i>Flavobacterium</i>	0.01683197	-0.016063			
ZOTU60: <i>Comamonadaceae</i>	0.01464276	-0.0490035			
ZOTU59: <i>Staphylococcus</i>	0.01459722	-0.0427289			
ZOTU145: <i>Intrasporangiaceae</i>	0.01459563	0.0033087			

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